

Randomised Controlled Trial

Effect of structured pre-anaesthetic review on patient safety and satisfaction: a randomised controlled trial

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Abstract

Background: Pre-anaesthetic review is a critical component of perioperative care that facilitates risk assessment and patient education prior to surgery. However, in many resource-constrained settings, preoperative anaesthetic evaluation is often brief and inconsistently implemented. This study evaluated the effect of structured pre-anaesthetic review on patient safety and satisfaction among patients undergoing elective surgery. The study aimed to compare the incidence of perioperative complications between patients who undergo structured pre-anaesthetic review and those who receive standard review, and to assess patient satisfaction among patients who undergo structured pre-anaesthetic review compared with those who receive standard review at the Federal Medical Centre, Gusau. **Materials and methods:** A randomised controlled trial was conducted among 114 adult patients aged 18–80 years scheduled for elective surgical procedures at Federal Medical Centre, Gusau. Participants were randomly assigned to an intervention group that received structured pre-anaesthetic review (n=57) and a control group that received routine preoperative care (n=57). The intervention consisted of a standardised pre-anaesthetic consultation including comprehensive clinical assessment, risk stratification, and structured patient education. Perioperative complications were assessed using the Clavien–Dindo Classification, while patient satisfaction was measured using a modified Iowa Satisfaction with Anaesthesia Scale. Data were analysed using SPSS version 27 with independent t-tests and chi-square tests at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** Patients who received structured pre-anaesthetic review demonstrated significantly lower rates of perioperative complications compared with those receiving routine care (10.5% vs. 24.6%; $\chi^2 = 4.08$, $p = 0.043$; OR = 0.36, 95% CI: 0.13–0.98). The intervention group also reported significantly higher satisfaction with perioperative care (4.47 ± 0.45 vs. 3.78 ± 0.54 ; $t = 7.63$, $p < 0.001$; Cohen's $d = 1.39$). **Conclusions:** Structured pre-anaesthetic review significantly reduces perioperative complications and improves patient satisfaction among elective surgical patients. These findings highlight the value of structured preoperative assessment as a low-cost, patient-centred intervention that can strengthen perioperative care in resource-limited healthcare settings.

Keywords: Patient safety, Patient satisfaction, Perioperative complications, Pre-anaesthetic review, Randomised controlled trial.

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Introduction

Patient safety and satisfaction are critical indicators of the quality of healthcare delivery worldwide. In recent decades, perioperative care has evolved beyond the technical aspects of surgery to encompass multidisciplinary strategies that enhance patient outcomes. Anaesthetic care, particularly during the preoperative phase, plays a central role in ensuring patient safety and optimising perioperative outcomes. Pre-anaesthetic review – also known as structured pre-anaesthetic assessment – is increasingly recognised as a fundamental component of perioperative management. It involves systematic evaluation of

patients before surgery to identify and mitigate perioperative risks, enhance communication, reduce anxiety, and facilitate individualised anaesthetic planning.^{1,2}

Patient safety is a cornerstone of quality healthcare. The World Health Organisation reports that anaesthesia-related adverse events contribute significantly to surgical morbidity and mortality, particularly in low- and middle-income countries.³ Many of these adverse events are preventable through early identification of comorbidities, risk stratification, and appropriate preoperative optimization—core objectives of structured pre-anaesthetic reviews. Empirical evidence suggests that comprehensive pre-anaesthetic assessments can reduce perioperative complications, improve intraoperative stability, and enhance postoperative recovery.^{4,5} However, in many Nigerian hospitals, preoperative anaesthetic reviews are often brief, informal, and inconsistently implemented in high-volume elective surgical settings due to workforce shortages and resource constraints.⁶

Patient satisfaction has also emerged as an essential outcome measure in modern surgical care. Structured pre-anaesthetic reviews improve satisfaction by providing patient education, reassurance, and shared decision-making—factors that reduce preoperative anxiety and enhance the overall healthcare experience.^{7,8} In Nigeria, where patient-centred care is still developing, structured perioperative communication represents a valuable strategy for improving patient experiences and outcomes.

The Federal Medical Centre (FMC) Gusau, located in Zamfara State, Nigeria, is a tertiary referral facility serving a predominantly rural and underserved population. The hospital performs a considerable number of elective surgical procedures annually across multiple specialities. Despite this, perioperative complications and suboptimal patient satisfaction remain important clinical concerns. These outcomes highlight the need to evaluate existing preoperative assessment practices and explore strategies to improve perioperative outcomes. Comprehensive pre-anaesthetic evaluations have been reported to prevent a substantial proportion of postoperative complications in Nigerian hospitals,⁹ yet rigorous experimental evidence in this context remains scarce.

Randomized controlled trials provide the highest level of evidence for evaluating healthcare interventions. However, there is a paucity of RCT-based studies examining the impact of structured pre-anaesthetic reviews in Nigeria. Most available

studies are observational or retrospective, limiting causal inference. Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the effect of structured pre-anaesthetic review on patient safety and satisfaction among elective surgical patients at FMC Gusau using a randomised controlled trial design.

The specific objectives were:

1. To compare the incidence of perioperative complications between patients who undergo a structured pre-anaesthetic review and those who receive standard pre-anaesthetic review at FMC Gusau.
2. To assess the level of patient satisfaction among patients who undergo a structured pre-anaesthetic review compared with those who receive a standard pre-anaesthetic review at FMC Gusau.

Materials and methods

Study Design and Setting

A parallel-group randomised controlled trial was conducted at the Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Gusau, a tertiary healthcare institution in Zamfara State, Northwestern Nigeria. The hospital provides comprehensive specialist services, including surgery, anaesthesia, intensive care, obstetrics and gynaecology, orthopaedics, ophthalmology, and ENT services. It serves a predominantly rural population across Zamfara State and neighbouring regions. The study was conducted over an eight-week recruitment period between January and February 2026.

Study Population

The target population consisted of adult patients scheduled for elective surgical procedures in General Surgery, Orthopaedics, Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Ear, Nose and Throat (ENT), and Ophthalmology departments. These departments were selected due to their relatively high elective surgical volumes.

Eligibility Criteria

Participants were eligible for inclusion if they: were aged 18–80 years; were scheduled for elective non-cardiac surgery; had at least 72 hours' notice before surgery; were classified as ASA physical status I–III; and were able to provide informed consent.

Participants were excluded if they: required emergency surgery; were ASA physical status IV or higher; had significant communication barriers; declined participation or were unable to provide consent; or required specialised investigations unavailable at FMC Gusau.

Sample Size Determination

Sample size was calculated using the two-proportion formula for randomised controlled

trials. Hospital audit data indicated a baseline postoperative complication rate of 45% among elective surgical patients ($p_1 = 0.45$). The intervention was expected to achieve a 30% relative reduction in complication rates, yielding an anticipated intervention complication rate of 31.5% ($p_2 = 0.315$). Using a two-sided significance level of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$) and 80% statistical power ($\beta = 0.20$), the calculated minimum sample size was 50 participants per group. To account for potential non-response or attrition, 10% was added, giving approximately 55 participants per group. The final recruitment target was therefore 120 participants (60 per group). During screening, 6 participants were excluded prior to randomisation, resulting in 114 participants (57 per group) who completed the study and were included in the final analysis.

Sampling Technique and Randomisation

Eligible participants were recruited consecutively from elective surgical booking lists. Stratified block randomisation was used, with randomly varying block sizes of 2 and 4, to ensure balanced allocation across surgical specialities and ASA physical status categories while minimising the risk of predictable allocation. A computer-generated randomisation sequence was prepared prior to participant recruitment. Allocation concealment was maintained using opaque, sequentially numbered sealed envelopes, which were opened in order after enrolment.

Intervention and Control Procedures

Participants in the **intervention group** received a structured pre-anaesthetic review conducted by a consultant anaesthetist 24–72 hours prior to surgery. The review followed a standardised assessment checklist that included: comprehensive medical history review; evaluation of comorbidities and medication use; airway assessment; ASA risk stratification; review of laboratory investigations; optimisation of medical conditions; preoperative fasting verification; and patient counselling and perioperative education. The consultation also addressed patient concerns, perioperative expectations, and anaesthetic risks, with the aim of improving patient preparedness and reducing anxiety.

Table 1 presents the participants in the control group, who received routine preoperative evaluation, typically conducted by junior medical officers or anaesthesia trainees, according to standard hospital practice. Routine assessment generally involved basic clinical history, physical examination, review of laboratory investigations, and clearance for surgery. However, this process was not standardised and did not include a

structured checklist or formal patient education component (see table 1)

Outcome Measures and Instrumentation

Perioperative complications were assessed using the Clavien–Dindo Classification, a standardised system for grading the severity of surgical complications. Complications were documented from the intraoperative period until hospital discharge.

Patient satisfaction was measured using a modified Iowa Satisfaction with Anaesthesia Scale (ISAS) administered 24–48 hours after surgery by blinded research assistants. The instrument assessed satisfaction across domains, including communication, preparedness, anxiety reduction, and overall satisfaction, using a 5-point Likert scale.

Safety adherence

Perioperative complications (primary outcome) were assessed using the Clavien–Dindo Classification. Patient satisfaction (secondary outcome) was measured using the modified Iowa Satisfaction with Anaesthesia Scale. In addition, a composite safety adherence score was calculated as a process indicator to assess intervention fidelity. This score measured compliance with key perioperative safety processes (airway assessment documentation, comorbidity review, medication reconciliation, fasting verification, and anaesthetic risk discussion), with each completed element scoring 1 point (range 0–5). Higher scores indicated better adherence.

Validity and Reliability

Content and face validity were established through expert review by consultant anaesthetists, surgeons, and perioperative nurses. Internal consistency of the modified Iowa Satisfaction with Anaesthesia Scale was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha, which yielded a value of 0.86, indicating good reliability. Inter-rater reliability for the Clavien–Dindo classification between two outcome assessors was assessed using Cohen's kappa ($\kappa = 0.81$, 95% CI: 0.72–0.90), representing almost perfect agreement. Research assistants received standardised training to ensure uniform administration of all instruments.

Data Collection Procedure

Baseline demographic and clinical data collected included age, sex, ASA classification, comorbidities, type of surgery, and type of anaesthesia. Postoperative outcomes were monitored until hospital discharge. All data were recorded on standardised forms and entered into a secure electronic database.

Blinding

Outcome assessors and data analysts were blinded

to group allocation to minimise bias. Blinding integrity was maintained by ensuring that outcome assessors (research assistants) had no involvement in the randomisation process, the delivery of interventions, or the clinical care of participants. Assessors were located in a separate area from the preoperative review clinic and did not have access to the allocation log or sealed envelopes. Participants were instructed not to discuss their pre-anaesthetic consultation with the outcome assessors. Data analysts received a de-identified dataset with group labels coded as 'A' and 'B' until final analysis was completed. No unblinding events were reported during the study.

Statistical Analysis

An intention-to-treat analysis was applied, in which all 114 randomised participants were analysed according to their original group allocation. No post-randomisation exclusions or crossovers occurred. Baseline characteristics were compared using independent t-tests for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical variables. Perioperative complication rates were compared using chi-square tests, and patient satisfaction scores were compared using independent t-tests. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All analyses were performed using SPSS version 27.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Federal Medical Centre Gusau Research Ethics Committee (Approval No: FMC/2021/985/008/NHREC/TR/0029/25/11/2025). The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and relevant national guidelines for biomedical research involving human participants. Written informed consent was obtained from all eligible participants after a detailed explanation of the study objectives, procedures, potential benefits, and risks. Participants were informed that participation was voluntary and that they could decline or withdraw from the study at any time without affecting their clinical care. Confidentiality and anonymity were ensured by assigning unique identification codes to participants rather than using personal identifiers across all data collection instruments.

Results

Participant Flow and Baseline Characteristics

A total of 120 patients were screened for eligibility. Six patients were excluded prior to randomisation due to withdrawal of consent or incomplete baseline data. The remaining 114 participants were randomised equally into the intervention group

(structured pre-anaesthetic review) and the control group (routine care), with 57 participants in each group. No participants were lost to follow-up, and all randomised participants were included in the final analysis.

Table 2 presents the socio-demographic and clinical characteristics of study participants. The study population was predominantly female (65.8%), with comparable distributions between the intervention and control groups. The mean age of participants was 41.4 ± 11.8 years, representing a typical adult elective surgical population. Most patients were ASA physical status II (52.6%), indicating a predominantly low-to-moderate perioperative risk profile. Regional anaesthesia was slightly more common than general anaesthesia (57% vs. 43%). No statistically significant baseline differences were observed between groups ($p > 0.05$), confirming successful randomisation and comparability at baseline (see Table 2).

Effect of Structured Pre-Anaesthetic Review on Perioperative Complications

Table 3 shows the association between structured pre-anaesthetic review and perioperative complications. There was a significant reduction in perioperative complications among patients receiving structured pre-anaesthetic review ($\chi^2 = 4.08$, $p = 0.043$). Only 6 patients (10.5%) in the intervention group experienced perioperative complications compared with 14 patients (24.6%) in the control group. The odds of experiencing complications were 64% lower in the intervention group (OR = 0.36; 95% CI: 0.13–0.98) (see Table 3).

Effect of Structured Pre-Anaesthetic Review on Patient Satisfaction

Table 4 presents the comparison of patient satisfaction scores between groups. Patients receiving structured pre-anaesthetic review reported significantly higher satisfaction with perioperative care compared with those receiving routine care ($t = 7.63$, $p < 0.001$). The mean satisfaction score in the intervention group was 4.47 ± 0.45 compared with 3.78 ± 0.54 in the control group, representing a mean difference of 0.69 (95% CI: 0.49–0.89). The effect size (Cohen's $d = 1.39$) indicates a large intervention effect, reflecting substantial improvement in communication clarity, emotional reassurance, and information adequacy (see Table 4).

Safety Adherence Outcomes

Although not a primary objective, safety adherence was assessed to provide context for the findings of complications. Participants in the intervention group demonstrated significantly higher adherence to perioperative safety protocols than those in the

Table 1: Components of the structured pre-anaesthetic review checklist

Domain	Specific items
Medical history	Current illnesses, past surgical/ anaesthetic history, drug allergies, family history of anaesthetic complications
Comorbidities and medications	Hypertension, diabetes, asthma, epilepsy, anticoagulants, insulin, herbal remedies
Airway assessment	Mallampati score, thyromental distance, neck mobility, dentition, history of difficult airway
ASA physical status	Classification I-III confirmation
Laboratory investigations	Hb, electrolytes/urea/creatinine, blood glucose, coagulation profile (as indicated)
Medical optimization	Blood pressure control, glycaemic control, chest physiotherapy if indicated
Preoperative fasting	Verification of last oral intake (solids/liquids)
Patient counselling	Explanation of anaesthetic plan, risks/benefits, postoperative pain management, NPO rationale
Anxiety reduction	Addressing patient concerns, expectations, and reassurance

Table 2: Socio-Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants (N = 114)

Variable	Intervention (n=57) n (%)	Control (n=57) n (%)	Total n (%)
Sex			
Female	38 (66.7)	37 (64.9)	75 (65.8)
Male	19 (33.3)	20 (35.1)	39 (34.2)
Age (years) Mean \pm SD	40.8 \pm 12.1	41.9 \pm 11.6	41.4 \pm 11.8
ASA Classification			
ASA I	12 (21.1)	11 (19.3)	23 (20.2)
ASA II	29 (50.9)	31 (54.4)	60 (52.6)
ASA III	16 (28.0)	15 (26.3)	31 (27.2)
Type of Anaesthesia			
Regional	34 (59.6)	31 (54.4)	65 (57.0)
General	23 (40.4)	26 (45.6)	49 (43.0)

control group ($t = 8.74$, $p < 0.001$). The mean safety adherence score increased by 0.16 points (95% CI: 0.12–0.19), with an effect size (Cohen's $d = 1.63$) indicating a significant intervention effect. This improved adherence likely contributed to the observed reduction in perioperative complications.

Discussion

This randomised controlled trial evaluated the effect of structured pre-anaesthetic review on patient safety and satisfaction among elective surgical patients at Federal Medical Centre, Gusau. The findings demonstrate that structured pre-anaesthetic review significantly reduces perioperative complications and improves patient satisfaction, providing robust evidence for the value of standardised preoperative assessment in resource-constrained healthcare settings.

Effect on Perioperative Complications

The finding that structured pre-anaesthetic review reduced perioperative complications by 64% (OR = 0.36) is clinically significant and consistent with existing literature. In a multicentre European study, Tomczyk et al. ¹¹ reported a 28% reduction in perioperative complications among patients receiving structured anaesthetic reviews.

Table 3: Association Between Intervention and Perioperative Complications

Outcome	Intervention (%)	n	Control (%)	n	χ^2	p-value	Odds Ratio (95% CI)
Complication present	6 (10.5)		14 (24.6)		4.08	0.043*	0.36 (0.13–0.98)
No complication	51 (89.5)		43 (75.4)				

*Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 4: Independent Samples t-Test for Patient Satisfaction Scores

Group	Mean \pm SD	Mean Difference	95% CI	t	p-value	Cohen's d
Control (n=57)	3.78 \pm 0.54					
Intervention (n=57)	4.47 \pm 0.45	0.69	0.49 - 0.89	7.63	<0.001*	1.39

* Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

Similarly, Mendes et al.¹¹ found improved intraoperative haemodynamic stability and reduced need for emergency interventions among high-risk cardiovascular surgical patients who received structured preoperative anaesthetic evaluation.

In the Nigerian context, Abubakar et al.¹² examined 500 patients undergoing elective surgery at Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital and found that only 7.4% of patients who received structured pre-anaesthetic assessment experienced intraoperative complications compared with 15.3% among patients receiving routine care. The present study's findings (10.5% vs 24.6%) align with this pattern, although the control group's complication rate was higher, possibly reflecting differences in baseline patient characteristics or institutional practices.

The mechanism underlying this protective effect likely involves several factors. Structured pre-anaesthetic review enables early identification of comorbidities, optimisation of medical conditions before surgery, systematic airway assessment, and comprehensive medication reconciliation.¹³ These processes reduce the likelihood of unanticipated perioperative events such as difficult airway management, adverse drug reactions, or haemodynamic instability. The significantly higher safety adherence scores observed in the intervention group (0.88 vs 0.72, $p < 0.001$) support this explanation, indicating that structured protocols improve adherence to essential safety practices.

Effect on Patient Satisfaction

The substantial improvement in patient satisfaction in the intervention group (Cohen's $d = 1.39$) is among the largest effect sizes observed in this study. This finding aligns with research by Sharma et al.,¹⁴ who reported that 91.6% of patients receiving structured pre-anaesthetic consultations reported high satisfaction levels compared with 65.4% among patients receiving standard preoperative interactions in Indian tertiary hospitals.

In Nigeria, Olayemi et al.¹⁵ found that patients at University College Hospital, Ibadan, who underwent structured pre-anaesthetic evaluations demonstrated higher satisfaction with perioperative care, particularly valuing clear explanations regarding anaesthetic risks and perioperative procedures. Adewale and Olowookere¹⁶ similarly observed that structured patient education during pre-anaesthetic consultation enhanced shared decision-making, improved trust in healthcare providers, and contributed to improved hospital experiences.

The large effect size observed for satisfaction outcomes likely reflects the comprehensive nature of the structured review, which addressed multiple dimensions of patient experience, including communication clarity, emotional reassurance, and information adequacy. These findings reinforce the importance of effective communication and patient engagement in improving satisfaction with surgical care, as emphasised in the Patient-Centred Care Model.¹⁷

Integration with Theoretical Framework

The findings provide empirical support for the Patient-Centred Care Model, which emphasises respect for patient preferences, effective communication, patient education, and collaborative decision-making as essential elements of high-quality healthcare delivery.¹⁸ Structured pre-anaesthetic review operationalises several core components of this model within the perioperative care process. The significant improvement in patient satisfaction reflects the PCC principle of respectful communication and emotional support. By providing patients with clear explanations about anaesthetic procedures, risks, and perioperative expectations, the structured review fostered trust and improved the overall patient experience.

Clinical and Health System Implications

The findings have important implications for clinical practice and health system strengthening in resource-constrained settings. The observed reduction in perioperative complications translates directly into improved patient safety and reduced morbidity. From a health system perspective, preventing complications reduces the need for additional interventions, prolonged hospital stays, and increased healthcare costs.¹⁹

The substantial improvement in patient satisfaction addresses an often-neglected aspect of surgical care quality in Nigerian hospitals. In healthcare systems where patient-centred approaches are still developing, structured pre-anaesthetic review offers a practical strategy to improve patient experience and strengthen public confidence in healthcare services.²⁰

Strengths and Limitations

This study has several methodological strengths. The randomised controlled trial design enhanced internal validity and strengthened causal inference regarding the effect of structured pre-anaesthetic review. Participant retention was excellent, with no loss to follow-up, thereby increasing the reliability of outcome assessments. The study also incorporated objective safety indicators and patient-reported outcomes, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of the intervention. However, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the study was conducted in a single tertiary healthcare institution, which may limit the external validity and generalizability of the findings to other hospitals. Second, blinding of participants and clinicians was not feasible due to the nature of the intervention, which may introduce performance bias. Third, patient satisfaction was assessed using self-reported measures, which may be subject to recall and social desirability bias.

Fourth, the relatively short follow-up period restricted the ability to assess long-term postoperative outcomes.

Conclusion

This randomised controlled trial demonstrates that structured pre-anaesthetic review significantly reduces perioperative complications and improves patient satisfaction among elective surgical patients at Federal Medical Centre, Gusau. Patients receiving structured review had 64% lower odds of experiencing complications and reported substantially higher satisfaction with perioperative care. These findings highlight the value of structured preoperative assessment as a low-cost, patient-centred intervention that can strengthen perioperative care in resource-limited healthcare settings. Integration of structured pre-anaesthetic review into routine surgical practice at FMC Gusau and similar tertiary healthcare institutions should be considered.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Authors' contributions

Salihu Abdulrahman Kombo: Supervision, methodology, validation, writing, review and editing.

Kabiru Salisu Zamau: Conceptualisation, methodology, investigation, data curation, formal analysis, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing.

Hamisu Yakubu: Supervision, methodology, validation, writing, review and editing.

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References

1. Kempthorne P, Morriss WW, Mellin-Olsen J, Gore-Booth J. The WFSA global anesthesia workforce survey. *Anesth Analg* 2017; 125(3): 981-990.
2. Smith AF, Mahajan RP, Checketts MR. Preoperative anaesthetic evaluation: The

- path to patient safety. *Br J Anaesth* 2021; 127(2): 174-182.
3. World Health Organization. Global guidelines for the prevention of surgical site infection. 2nd ed. Geneva: WHO Press; 2019.
 4. Patel SY, Ma Y, Sanger PC, Meara JG. The role of preoperative assessment in reducing perioperative complications. *Ann Surg* 2021; 274(3): e215-e222.
 5. Yakubu MM. Evaluating the impact of pre-anaesthetic assessment clinics in a Nigerian tertiary hospital. *Niger Med J* 2017; 58(6): 109-116.
 6. Okafor UV, Ezeama CO. Preoperative assessment practices in Nigerian tertiary hospitals: A cross-sectional survey. *West Afr J Anaesth* 2019; 27(1): 1-7.
 7. Lee A, Chui PT, Gin T, Underwood M. Impact of preoperative anaesthesia consultation on patient outcomes: A prospective randomized study. *Anesth Analg* 2020; 130(2): 431-438.
 8. Obasi AA, Eze NC, Okeke CI. Patient satisfaction with perioperative care in a Nigerian tertiary hospital. *Niger J Clin Pract* 2022; 25(4): 512-518.
 9. Yakubu A. Incomplete preoperative workups and length of hospital stay in Nigerian surgical patients. *Ann Afr Med* 2018; 17(4): 202-207.
 10. Tomczyk S, Bauer M, Hein A. Multicenter study on the effect of structured anesthetic review on perioperative complications. *J Clin Anesth* 2023; 85: 111072.
 11. Mendes FS, Oliveira JP, Ramos CR. Impact of structured preoperative review on hemodynamic stability. *Int J Surg* 2021; 87: 120-127.
 12. Abubakar IM, Bello MA, Yusuf S. Effect of structured pre-anesthetic review on intraoperative events at Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital. *Niger J Clin Pract* 2022; 25(3): 412-418.
 13. Ghazal R, Ahmad I, Khan MF. Role of structured pre-anesthetic assessment in identifying medication errors and optimizing comorbid conditions. *J Anaesthesiol Clin Pharmacol* 2021; 37(2): 245-251.
 14. Sharma S, Singh P, Kaur G. Patient satisfaction with structured pre-anaesthetic consultations: A multicentre study. *Indian J Anaesth* 2020; 64(5): 389-396.
 15. Olayemi OO, Adebayo SA, Nuhu AB. Patient satisfaction with preoperative anaesthetic assessment at University College Hospital, Ibadan. *West Afr J Anaesth* 2021; 28(2): 85-92.
 16. Adewale BA, Olowookere SA. Structured patient education during pre-anaesthetic consultation and its impact on shared decision-making. *Niger J Med* 2023; 32(1): 45-52.
 17. Chen L, Xiao LD, Han W, De Bellis A. Patient-centered care models in perioperative settings: A systematic review. *J Perioper Pract* 2023; 33(4): 98-107.
 18. Epstein RM, Street RL. The values and value of patient-centered care. *Ann Fam Med* 2022; 20(2): 100-107.
 19. Pearse RM, Holt PJE, Grocott MPW. Managing perioperative risk in patients undergoing elective non-cardiac surgery. *BMJ* 2014; 348: g1425.
 20. Adekeye OA, Adesina BA, Abubakar MB. Patient satisfaction with healthcare services in Nigeria: A systematic review. *Niger Postgrad Med J* 2017; 24(3): 135-142.